

Cyclic Voltammetric Studies of Cadmium(II) in Presence of Glycine

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Complexes of cadmium(II) with glycine and other amino acids have been studied with the help of polarographic and potentiometric techniques¹.

Cyclic voltammetry has been shown to be the best technique for qualitative investigations of complexation reactions. Also one obtains direct evidence for the formation of intermediate species. In the present communication we report the cyclic voltammetric study of complexation reactions between cadmium(II)-glycine complex system.

Results and Discussion

Cyclic voltammograms were recorded in presence of glycine medium at different concentrations. The formal electrode potential (E_f) used for calculation, was taken as the average of anodic and cathodic peak potentials. It was found that the formal potentials of Cd^{II} shifted towards more negative direction on increasing the concentration of ligand. The E_f values at different concentrations of glycine are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CATHODIC, ANODIC AND FORMAL ELECTRODE POTENTIAL VALUES OF Cd^{II} IN Cd^{II} -GLYCINATE SYSTEM			Potential (V) vs SCE		
[Glycine] $\times 10^3$	[Glycinate] $\times 10^3$	$-\log [\bar{X}]$ (glycine)	Cathodic E_{pc}	Anodic E_{pa}	Formal E_f
—	—	—	-0.615	-0.580	-0.598
1.0	0.18	2.744 7	-0.745	-0.685	-0.715
2.0	0.35	2.455 9	-0.755	-0.700	-0.728
4.0	0.69	2.161 2	-0.780	-0.730	-0.755
8.0	1.39	1.857 0	-0.810	-0.760	-0.785
16.0	2.78	1.556 0	-0.830	-0.780	-0.805
24.0	4.16	1.380 9	-0.845	-0.795	-0.820
32.0	5.55	1.255 7	-0.855	-0.805	-0.830
40.0	6.94	1.158 6	-0.865	-0.815	-0.840

Concentration of $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ is 4×10^{-4} M.

The plots of E_f vs $\log [\bar{X}]$ (free ligand) appeared as a smooth curve indicating the formation of multiple complex species. A typical plot of cadmium-glycine is given in Fig. 1. The formation

constants of consecutive complexes were calculated by employing DeFord and Hume² equation in which the terms for half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) were replaced by formal potential (E_f) terms.

$$Fo(x) = 1 + \beta_1(x) + \beta_2(x)^2 + \beta_3(x)^3 \quad (1)$$

$$= \text{Antilog } 0.435 \frac{nF}{RT} (E_f)_s - (E_f)_c + \log I_s/I_c \quad (2)$$

$$(x) = \frac{\text{Acid}}{1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_1} + \frac{[\text{H}^{+2}]}{K_1 K_2}} \quad (3)$$

where I_s is the current without the addition of ligand and I_c the current in complex stage means after the addition of ligand.

Fig. 1. Plots of $-\log [\bar{X}]$ vs E_f (cadmium-glycine system).

Using the above equations the values of (x) were calculated at different concentrations of glycinate

[ion \bar{X}] from the experimental values given in Table 1. The concentration of ligand ion \bar{X} was calculated from the reported dissociation constants of glycine ($pK: 2.350$; $pK: 9.779$)³. The values of β_1 , β_2 and β_3 were calculated by extrapolating the values at $\bar{X}=0$ in the plots of $F_1(x)$ and $F_2(x)$ and $F_3(x)$ vs \bar{X} respectively (Fig. 2). Employing the above method we have determined the overall stability constants of Cd^{II}-glycine complex system (Table 2).

TABLE 2—OVERALL FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Cd^{II}-GLYCINE COMPLEXES

Constant	Observed at 35°	Reported* at 25°
$\log \beta_1$	6.60	4.36
$\log \beta_2$	7.95	7.99
$\log \beta_3$	10.00	10.13

*Ref. 4.

Fig. 2. Plots of $F(x)$ vs \bar{X} (ligand concentration): (OA) $F_1(\bar{X})$ vs \bar{X} , (□B) $F_2(x)$ vs \bar{X} and (△C) vs \bar{X} (cadmium-glycine system).

The values of $\log \beta_2$ and $\log \beta_3$ agree fairly well with the reported values whereas the values of $\log \beta_1$, appears somewhat higher. The higher values of $\log \beta_1$ may be attributed to the dynamic nature of the method employed.

Experimental

A cyclic voltammograph (CV-1, Bionalytical Systems) in combination with an X-Y recorder (Digilog) was used to record the cyclic voltammograms keeping the scan rate constant at 40 mV s^{-1} . A special voltammetric cell made from corning glass having three-electrode assembly was used. A hanging mercury drop electrode, HMDE was used as the working electrode while a platinum spiral acted as the auxiliary electrode. All electrode potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode which was connected to the test solution through a sodium nitrate salt-bridge. The experiments were carried out at $35 \pm 1^\circ$.

Reagent grade chemicals were used. The stock solution of Cd^{II} was prepared in triple-distilled water. The test solutions of desired concentrations, were prepared from 0.01 M stock solution of cadmium nitrate. In all the observations the concentration of Cd^{II} was kept at $4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, while 0.1 M KCl solution was used as supporting electrolyte.

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References

1. A. I. KOSTROMINE and V.A. VEKSLINE, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1956, 1, 2385; G. N. RAO and R. S. SUBRAHMANYA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1962, 31, 55; *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1964, 60, 165; M. RUDOLF G. AVEL and M. HERBERT, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, 241, 240; T. P. RADHAKRISHNAN, S. C. SARAIYA and A. K. SUNDARAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 521; G. P. SAXENA and S. S. SINGH, *Lab. Dev., Part A*, 1969; R. C. KAPOOR, S. L. JAIN and JAI KISHAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, 18, 133.
2. D. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUME, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 5321.
3. C. D. HODGMAN, "Hand Book of Chemistry and Physics", 1992, 1761.
4. E. BOTTARI, *Ann. Chim. (Rome)*, 1976, 66, 677.